
90. Astrophysics of our Galaxy

ALMOST 20 YEARS ago, the Geneva–Copenhagen spectroscopic survey established a major advance in characterising the nearby stellar population: it was a magnitude-limited (~ 8.4 mag), and kinematically unbiased sample of F and G stars within about 40 pc, yielding ages, metallicities, and kinematic properties of around 14 000 such stars in the solar neighbourhood (Nordström et al., 2004).

Among many subsequent applications, they revisited the age–metallicity, age–velocity, and metallicity–velocity relations of the solar neighbourhood. It was, they said, a data set ‘... *unlikely to be superseded in essential respects until the results of the Gaia mission and/or the RAVE project become available*’. That time has come.

IN MY PREVIOUS essay I summarised how astrophysical parameters are being estimated from the totality of Gaia data, resulting in (for example) spectroscopic and evolutionary parameters for up to 470 million stars.

Since the publication of this Data Release 3 in June 2022, several papers have published some early results, illustrating how these data are providing a totally new insight in understanding the structure, formation, and evolution of huge numbers of stars in our Galaxy. I will present here just a few of these, based on two specific data samples, to give a flavour of what Gaia is providing.

THE FIRST SAMPLE was constructed and discussed by Recio-Blanco et al. (2022b). It makes use exclusively of the stellar parameters and chemical abundances derived from the Gaia RVS spectra by the GSP-Spec module, described briefly in essay #89.

The second is the ‘Golden Sample’ of Creevey et al. (2022). This utilises all relevant Gaia data, i.e. mean (calibrated) BP and RP spectra, and the mean (calibrated) RVS spectra, along with astrometry (distances and proper motions) and photometry (G , G_{BP} , G_{RP}).

The latter comprises six carefully defined subsets of around 3 million young massive disk (OBA) stars, 3 million FGKM stars, 20 000 ultra-cool dwarfs, and smaller numbers of 15 740 carbon stars, 5863 solar analogues, and a sample of spectrophotometric standard stars.

THE FIRST THREE IMAGES are examples of the stellar characterisation provided by the radial velocity spectrometer data, the first two from Recio-Blanco et al. (2022a), the other from Recio-Blanco et al. (2022b).

The first shows the distribution, in Galactic coordinates, of effective temperatures, T_{eff} , throughout the Galaxy, for their 5.6 million stars. It shows the giant star population dominating the Galactic disk and bulge regions. In-plane interstellar extinction leaves its imprint on the underlying populations: in higher extinction regions, cool giant stars at large distances become too faint in the RVS wavelength domain, and the median of the temperature distribution becomes hotter. Nearby fainter dwarf stars in the foreground dominate the regions above and below the Galactic plane, increasing the median T_{eff} values.

The analogue of the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram showing surface gravity, $\log(g)$, versus T_{eff} (the Kiel diagram), is shown here, colour coded according to star density. The parameters’ precision is evident from the well-defined evolutionary sequences. For example, the clear ‘red clump’ presents a metallicity dependence that is independent from that of the red giant branch, as expected. Additionally, younger, more massive stars populate the hotter metal-rich sequence with $\log(g) \lesssim 3$. These stars are located in the Milky Way spiral arms.

My third example from the RVS data shows Galactic stars in the GSP-Spec database, colour-coded according to the median stellar metallicity, $[M/H]$. In the Galactic plane, the higher metallicity of the thin disk is evident.

In the central regions of the Galaxy, there is a more metal-poor mix of bulge and thick disk populations while, far from the plane, there are both nearby high-metallicity thin disk stars, and more distant metal-poor halo stars.

THE NEXT FOUR IMAGES are examples taken from the ‘Golden Sample’ of Creevey et al. (2022). Again, I include them as representative illustrations of the huge wealth of information contained in these catalogues.

Firstly, their O-, B- and A-type (OBA) star sample yielded 3 023 388 sources (compared with 34 055 from a pre-Gaia SIMBAD query). It was constructed as being the best targets to study the structure and dynamics of star-forming regions, as well as of the Galactic spiral arms. This is because, being of intermediate to large mass, they evolve rapidly, and hence typically do not migrate far from their birth association or cluster.

The figure shows their transverse velocities constructed from their distances and proper motions, with thin disk stars ‘defined’ as having tangential velocities $v_{\text{tan}} < 40 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, thick disk stars as $40 < v_{\text{tan}} < 180 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and halo stars having $v_{\text{tan}} > 180 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The vertical dashed lines indicate these transverse velocity limits, and these correspond well to the inflections in the histograms for this hot star sample.

STARS OF F, G, K, and M spectral type form the majority of the stars of our own Galaxy. They hold a record of how our Galaxy was formed, and how it has evolved. Their sample (constructed using constraints on T_{eff} , $\log(g)$, $[M/H]$, radius, mass, age, evolutionary stage, and spectral type), contains 6.3 million stars, which is shown here as a projection on the Galactic plane.

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ULTRACOOL DWARFS (UCDs), defined as sources with spectral types M7 or later, are objects at the faint end of the main sequence. The class includes the coolest hydrogen-burning stars, as well as brown dwarfs. Despite a fundamental differences in internal structure across this stellar/sub-stellar regime, the atmospheric properties overlap at the boundary, and it has been difficult to distinguish between the two based on photometric or spectroscopic properties alone.

For their high-quality sample of 21 068 sources, they complemented T_{eff} with radii inferred from the Stefan–Boltzmann law (making use of infrared photometry). This figure, showing radii as a function of T_{eff} , suggests a clear minimum in the mass–radius relation at $T_{\text{eff}} \sim 2000 \text{ K}$.

MY FINAL EXAMPLE from their work is of carbon stars. These are a class of Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) stars having C-enriched atmospheres, showing strong C_2 and CN molecular bands either due to mass transfer in binary systems, or to the pollution by nuclear He fusion products from the inner to the outer layers.

Because they belong to a late stage of stellar evolution where mass-loss occurs, carbon stars are important contributors to the interstellar medium, and provide good reference cases to study the physical processes affecting the end of the life of low-mass stars.

Their sample of 15 740 carbon stars is shown here in Galactic coordinates. It reveals a strong concentration towards the Galactic plane, with others in the Magellanic Clouds, and the Sagittarius stream.

